

Methodology for improving the technical preparation of greco-roman wrestlers at the initial training stage

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Abstract

Purpose: To improve the technical preparation of Greco-Roman wrestlers at the initial training stage and to determine the effective sequence for teaching technical skills in standing and parterre positions.

Methods: The research process utilized analysis of scientific and methodological literature, questionnaires, pedagogical observation, and analysis. A survey was conducted among 40 coaches with varying levels of experience to study their opinions on organizing training at the initial stage.

Results: According to the research findings, it was determined to be appropriate to involve Greco-Roman wrestlers in training from the age of 9 at the initial training stage. It is considered effective to conduct training sessions 3 times a week in the first academic year and 4 times a week in the second. Additionally, to enhance the wrestlers' technical preparation, a system was developed for the phased teaching of a total of 18 technical skills in standing and parterre positions over a three-year training process.

Conclusion: In developing the technical preparation of Greco-Roman wrestlers at the initial training stage, it is crucial to teach technical methods sequentially according to their level of complexity. First teaching attacking techniques from a standing position, then techniques in the parterre position, followed by defensive and counter-attacking actions, serves to effectively form the technical mastery of young wrestlers.

Keywords: Greco-Roman wrestling, initial training stage, technical preparation, standing position, parterre position, training process, technical methods.

Introduction

In our republic, large-scale work is being carried out to actively develop physical culture and sports, to involve all segments of the population, especially youth, in regular physical education and mass sports, and to promote a healthy lifestyle in society. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-22, dated January 21, 2026, "On Measures for the Further Development of Wrestling Sports," serves as a legal basis for elevating freestyle wrestling, Greco-Roman wrestling, and women's wrestling to a higher level in our country [1].

Greco-Roman wrestling is one of the

most famous and popular sports included in the Summer Olympic Games program, with thousands of athletes actively training on all five continents. The growing competition in Greco-Roman wrestling necessitates finding ways to increase the organizational and methodological effectiveness of managing all stages, from initial training to the highest levels of athletic mastery. The methodology for developing the technical skills of Greco-Roman wrestlers at the initial training stage and for correctly assessing training load norms has not been sufficiently explored from a scientific standpoint. This requires scientifically-grounded research by specialists.[2,3]

Today's sports results place high demands on the professional qualities of coaches at the initial training stage, including their knowledge and practical skills. This is because effectively organizing the initial stage of sports - which serves as an impetus for further athletic development, an extremely important foundation for training sports reserves, and a universal means of education - requires a search for more rational organizational forms, tools, and methods.

In recent years, significant changes have occurred in the content of competitive matches and the regulations of competitions. Perceptions regarding the specifics of teaching children complex technical-tactical actions and the methodology for training highly skilled athletes have also evolved. In modern Greco-Roman wrestling, match times have been shortened, the pace of wrestling has become more intense and faster, and continuous attacks are encouraged. This requires wrestlers to resolve technical-tactical problems very quickly and to apply specific offensive combinations of actions. However, the existing methodology for technical-tactical preparation does not adequately account for the demands of modern wrestling. Teaching technical-tactical actions during the initial training of Greco-Roman wrestlers is of great importance, serving as a practical program for each athlete's successful

Table 1. Results of the questionnaire survey of coaches conducting training sessions for Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage, identifying problems related to the structure of the sessions (n=40)

Answers	Qualified Coaches	n=40
Question 1. At what age do you consider it appropriate to admit Greco-Roman wrestlers to the initial training stage?		
A	From age 7	20%
B	From age 9	50%
V	From age 8	30%
Question 2. How many times a week do you conduct training sessions during the initial training stage (1st year)?		
A	Twice	0%
B	Three times	80%
V	Four times	20%
Question 3. How many times a week do you conduct training sessions during the initial training stage (2nd year)?		
A	Twice	0%
B	Three times	30%
V	Four times	70%
Question 4. Do you use age-appropriate active games and special exercises to develop the physical fitness of Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage?		
A	Yes	20%
B	No	50%
C	I cannot answer	30%
Question 5. Has a sequence of methods been developed for teaching techniques to Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage?		
A	Yes	10%
B	No	60%
C	I cannot answer	30%
Question 6. During the training process for Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage, which qualities do you focus on developing the most?		
A	Flexibility, agility, speed	60%
B	Strength, endurance, speed	20%
C	Strength, speed, flexibility	20%
Question 7. Which areas of preparation do you consider most appropriate to focus on for Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage?		
A	Physical preparation, technical preparation	70%
B	Technical-tactical preparation	20%
C	Psychological, technical preparation	10%
Question 8. Which muscle groups do you believe need to be better developed in Greco-Roman wrestlers during the initial training stage?		
A	Arm and shoulder girdle muscles	20%
B	Leg (thigh and calf) muscles	20%
C	Arm, back, and leg muscles	60%
Question 9. When should internal assessments and friendly match competitions be held?		
A	Once a week	10%
B	Once a month	60%
C	Once every two months	30%
Question 10. What methods do you most often use for the recovery of Greco-Roman wrestlers' bodies after training?		
A	Sleep, massage	70%
B	Wellness tourism	20%
C	Shower, swimming	10%

preparation for subsequent stages: the training stage, the sports mastery stage, and the higher sports mastery stage.

Result and discussion

We aimed to conduct scientific research on teaching technical movements to Greco-Roman wrestlers at the initial training stage.

According to the analysis of scientific and methodological literature, textbooks and methodical manuals on sport wrestling have been created by scientists from our country and other countries (F. Kerimov, A. Ruziyev, N. Tastanov, Z. Bakiyev, S. Adilov, A. Primbetov, Dj. Tashnazarov, B. Satipov, U. Jarilkapov, A. Yakupbayev).

B.A. Satipov conducted research on teaching technical-tactical methods to freestyle wrestlers in the initial training stage. However, this literature has not adequately researched the issues of teaching the effectiveness of technical-tactical actions for Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage [5].

To identify the training problems of Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage, a questionnaire survey was conducted, and the opinions of coaches were studied and analyzed (see Table 1). The survey was conducted with specialists who had coaching experience: ten with 3 years, ten with 4-5 years, ten with 6-10 years, and ten with more than 10 years.

Analyzing the results of the first question

Table 1. Knowledge and skills to be acquired within the program for developing athletes' knowledge and skills on ethical and legal rules

Answers	Qualified Coaches	n=40
Question 1. At what age do you consider it appropriate to admit Greco-Roman wrestlers to the initial training stage?		
A	From age 7	20%
B	From age 9	50%
V	From age 8	30%
Question 2. How many times a week do you conduct training sessions during the initial training stage (1st year)?		
A	Twice	0%
B	Three times	80%
V	Four times	20%
Question 2. How many times a week do you conduct training sessions during the initial training stage (2nd year)?		
A	Twice	0%
B	Three times	30%
V	Four times	70%
Question 4. Do you use age-appropriate active games and special exercises to develop the physical fitness of Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage?		
A	Yes	20%
B	No	50%
C	I cannot answer	30%
Question 5. Has a sequence of methods been developed for teaching techniques to Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage?		
A	Yes	10%
B	No	60%
C	I cannot answer	30%
Question 6. During the training process for Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage, which qualities do you focus on developing the most?		
A	Flexibility, agility, speed	60%
B	Strength, endurance, speed	20%
C	Strength, speed, flexibility	20%
Question 7. Which areas of preparation do you consider most appropriate to focus on for Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial training stage?		
A	Physical preparation, technical preparation	70%
B	Technical-tactical preparation	20%
C	Psychological, technical preparation	10%
Question 8. Which muscle groups do you believe need to be better developed in Greco-Roman wrestlers during the initial training stage?		
A	Arm and shoulder girdle muscles	20%
B	Leg (thigh and calf) muscles	20%
C	Arm, back, and leg muscles	60%
Question 9. When should internal assessments and friendly match competitions be held?		
A	Once a week	10%
B	Once a month	60%
C	Once every two months	30%
Question 10. What methods do you most often use for the recovery of Greco-Roman wrestlers' bodies after training?		
A	Sleep, massage	70%
B	Wellness tourism	20%
C	Shower, swimming	10%

of the survey, in response to our question, "At what age do you consider it appropriate to admit Greco-Roman wrestlers to the initial training stage?," 20% of the coaches answered "from age 7," 30% of the coaches answered "from age 8," while 50% of the coaches answered "from age 9." It is appropriate to involve Greco-Roman wrestlers in the training process from the age of 9 for the initial training stage.

When we analyze the second question of the survey, "How many times a week do you conduct training sessions during the initial training stage (1st year)?," 0% of the coaches answered "twice a week," while 80% of the coaches emphasized "three times a week," and 20% answered "four times a week." Holding training sessions three times a week during the

initial training stage (1st year) is of great importance for athletes' progression to the next stages.

In the third question of our survey, "How many times a week do you conduct training sessions during the initial preparation stage (2nd year)?," 0% of coaches responded twice a week, 30% of coaches responded three times a week, while 70% of coaches responded four times a week. Conducting training sessions four times a week during the initial preparation stage (2nd year) allows us to ensure athletes' transition to the next stages and helps them become skilled athletes.

To the fourth question of our survey, "Do you use age-specific active games and special exercises to develop the physical fitness of Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial

preparation stage?," 20% of coaches answered "yes," 50% answered "no," and 30% answered "I cannot answer."

To the fifth question of our survey, "Has a sequence of techniques been developed for teaching technical maneuvers to Greco-Roman wrestlers in the initial preparation stage?," 10% of coaches answered "yes," 60% answered "no," while 30% of coaches responded with "I cannot answer."

In response to the sixth question of our survey, "During training, which qualities do you focus on developing most in Greco-Roman wrestlers at the initial training stage?," 60% of coaches answered flexibility, agility, and speed; 20% of coaches answered strength, endurance, and speed; and 20% of coaches answered strength, speed, and flexibility.

To the seventh question of our survey, "Which areas of preparation do you consider most appropriate to focus on for Greco-Roman wrestlers at the initial training stage?," 70% of coaches answered physical and technical preparation. While 20% of coaches answered technical-tactical preparation, 10% answered psychological and technical preparation.

In response to the eighth question of our survey, "Which muscle groups in the bodies of Greco-Roman wrestlers do you believe should be better developed at the initial training stage?," 20% of coaches answered the arm and shoulder girdle muscles, 20% of coaches answered the leg (thigh and calf) muscles, and 60% of coaches answered the arm and leg muscles.

In the ninth question of our survey, "When should internal control and sparring match competitions be held?" 10% of the coaches responded "once a week," 60% of the coaches responded "once a month," and 30% of the coaches responded "once every two months."

In the tenth question of our survey, "What methods do you use most often to help wrestlers recover their bodies after training?" 70% of the coaches answered "sleep and massage," 20% answered "wellness tourism," and 10% answered "showering and swimming."

In the initial training stage, Greco-Roman wrestlers must master nine techniques in the standing position and nine techniques in the parterre position, for a total of eighteen techniques.

The majority of coaches are of the opinion that for the first year of training,

technical instruction should begin with the following standing techniques: transitioning an opponent to the parterre position by pulling their arm, transitioning to parterre by diving under the arm, and transitioning to parterre by securing the neck and arm and pulling from the front. Afterward, techniques in the parterre position are mastered: turning an opponent over by grabbing their waist, turning them over by running in a circle with a key-lock grip on their shoulder, and turning them over by securing their neck and arm and rolling them.

For the second year of study, instruction in technical methods from a standing position should begin with the following techniques: transitioning to parterre by grabbing the wrist and dropping in front, transitioning to the parterre position by wrapping an arm around the neck, and a shoulder throw. Then, techniques in the parterre position are mastered: a rollover by holding the arm and waist, a reverse rollover by grabbing the far shoulder and neck from the front-top, and a chest throw by securing the neck and arm together.

For the third year of study, instruction in technical methods from a standing position should begin with the following techniques: shoulder throws, waist throws, and throws by wrapping an arm around the neck. Then, techniques in the parterre position are mastered: a rollover with a reverse waist grip, a rollover with a waist grip, and a chest throw with a waist grip (see Table 2).

In matches conducted by Greco-Roman wrestlers, offensive actions bring great success. When executing them, athletes make relatively minor technical errors related to selecting the appropriate means for conducting the match according to the emerging situations and determining the most opportune moment to initiate the actions.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of data from the conducted research, the following conclusions were reached:

Based on an analysis of best practices and scientific-methodological literature, a sequence was established for improving the methods and tools used in the initial training stage. This sequence is based on the progression and interaction of technical maneuvers performed by Greco-Roman wrestlers in both standing and parterre positions. For Greco-Roman wrestlers in the

initial training stage, it is most effective to first teach stances, followed by the mastery of technical maneuvers in standing and parterre positions in the following order: first, learn to execute attacks; then, defense; and after that, counter-attacks. Following this, it is necessary to master these skills before moving on to the next stage.

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